

Finger Print Patterns in Nepali and Non-Nepali (Indians) Palms – A Comparative Study

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ABSTRACT

Finger prints are considered as the best tool of identification. Finger print evidence is by far the most effective and reliable evidence in the court of law. Two major aspects which prove the efficiency of finger prints are, the ridges formed during the foetal period do not change their course of alignment throughout the life of an individual until the skin is decomposed and the other one is two finger prints of either a same individual or two different individuals are never alike, they differ in their patterns and ridge characteristics. Due to its effectiveness or we can say its potential fingerprints are considered as conclusive evidence in the court of law. Present study is an attempt to analyze and correlate fingerprint patterns with gender and population differences. We have carried a study with 300 individuals among which 150 were Nepali and 150 were Non-Nepali (mostly Indian origin) belonging to different age groups. This study was carried out in Nepal and India. All the 10 fingerprint patterns were divided into Loops, Whorls and Arches. Results show that Loops are most commonly found fingerprint patterns and Arches are least common. There are significant group variations in fingerprint pattern (rt. hand) between nepali and non Nepali the differences is slightly significant. Group variation for left hand prints between Nepali & Non-Nepali are also highly significant. Group variation for both hands between Nepali & Non-Nepali are also highly significant.

Keyword: Populations, fingerprints, Nepali and Non-Nepali

INTRODUCTION

The skin covers the anterior surface of human hand and plantar surface of the human foot is different in the texture and appearance than the one which covers the rest of the human body. This skin on the palmar and plantar surface is continuously wrinkled with narrow minute ridges known as friction ridges. A finger print is an impression of the friction ridges on all parts. The dermal carvings or finger prints appear for the first time on the human fingers, palm, soles and toes from 12th to 16th week of embryonic development and their formation gets completed by the 14th week i.e. about the 6th foetal month. The ridges thus, formed during the foetal period do not change their course or alignment throughout the life of an individual, until destroyed by decomposition of the skin after death¹.

Various physical evidences used for identification are fingerprints, DNA profiling, lip marks, foot prints, bite marks etc. Fingerprints are constant and individualistic and form the most reliable criteria for identification. Finger prints follow the Locard's Principle of Exchange. The secretions in the fingerprints contain residues various chemicals and their metabolites which can be detected and used for the forensic purposes². They can be found in the scene of occurrence from which the presence of a suspect or a victim or any other person can easily be proved.

Fingerprints are now a day used in many of the offices, educational institutions to validate the presence of an individual.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study was carried out in Nepal and India, 300 persons were participated in the study voluntarily and their finger prints were collected. The fingerprints were taken using the stamp pad of CAMLIN Company of size 157×96 mm. The smeared palm and fingers of both hands were printed on a durable plain paper laid down on a pressure pad which consisted of ten different blocks for ten fingers of right hand and left hand respectively. Both rolled and plane prints of right and left hand were taken. After obtaining the finger prints the basic details such as name, age, ethnic details and sex was also gathered. Primary patterns (loops, whorl and arches) were observed with the help of a powerful hand lens. Blood groups of all the persons were also noted for further study. Each finger in the finger print slip was assigned a number, ex: The 1st number was given to the right thumb and 10th number to left little.

Observation

Particulars and frequencies of occurrence of various finger print patterns obtained in this study has been tabulated classified and analyzed as under.

Table 1: Number Of Persons In Nepali And Non-Nepali

	HINDU		MUSLIM		CHRISTIAN		TOTAL
	MALE	FEMALE	MALE	FEMALE	MALE	FEMALE	
NEPALI	74	64	10	02	00	00	150
NON-NEPALI	78	52	02	01	07	10	150
TOTAL	152	116	12	03	07	10	300

Table 2: Bilateral Variation In Types Of Finger Print Pattern Of Nepali Females (66)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
RIGHT HAND DIGITS	21	96	213	330
LEFT HAND DIGITIS	24	104	202	330
TOTAL	45	200	415	660

Chi-square value =0.82,df=2,p=>0.5

Not significant

Table 3: Bilateral Variation In Types Of Finger Print Pattern Of Nepali Males (84)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
RIGHT HAND DIGITS	13	176	231	420
LEFT HAND DIGITIS	14	138	268	420
TOTAL	27	314	499	840

Chi-square value =7.4,df=2,p=<0.05

Significant

Table 4: Bilateral Variation In Types Of Finger Print Pattern Of Nepali Both Sex(150)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
RIGHT HAND DIGITS	34	272	444	750
LEFT HAND DIGITIS	38	242	470	750
TOTAL	72(4.8%)	514(34.3%)	914(60.9%)	1500

Chi-square value =2.8,df=2,p=>0.5

Not significant

Table 5: Bilateral Variation In Types Of Finger Print Pattern Of Non-Nepali Females (63)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
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RIGHT HAND DIGITS	19	129	167	315
LEFT HAND DIGITIS	20	130	165	315
TOTAL	39	259	332	630

Chi-square value =0,df=2,p=>0.5

Not significant

Table 6: Bilateral Variation In Types Of Finger Print Pattern Of Non-Nepali Males (87)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
RIGHT HAND DIGITS	10	204	221	435
LEFT HAND DIGITIS	10	201	224	435
TOTAL	20	405	445	870

Chi-square value =0,df=2,p=>0.5

Not significant

Table 7: Bilateral Variation In Types Of Finger Print Pattern Of Non-Nepali Females Both Sex (150)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
RIGHT HAND DIGITS	29	333	388	750
LEFT HAND DIGITIS	30	331	389	750
TOTAL	59(3.9%)	664(44.3%)	777(51.8%)	1500

Chi-square value =0.82,df=2,p=>0.5

Not significant

Table 8: Group Variation In Types Of Finger Print(Rt.Hands) Pattern Between Nepali And Non- Nepali (150)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
RIGHT HAND DIGITS OF NEPALI	34	272	444	750
RIGHT HAND DIGITS OF NON-NEPALI	29	333	388	750
TOTAL	63	605	832	1500

Chi-square value =10.4,df=2,p=<0.01

significant at 1% level

Table 9: group variation in types of finger print pattern(lt.hand)between nepali and non-nepali (150)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
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LEFT HAND DIGITS OF NEPALI	38	242	470	750
LEFT HAND DIGITS OF NON-NEPALI	30	331	389	750
TOTAL	68	573	859	1500

Chi-square value =22.4,df=2,p=<0.001

Significant even at 0.1% level

Table 10: group variation in types of finger print pattern between nepali and non-nepali (300)

SIDE	ARCHES	WHORLES	LOOPS	TOTAL
NEPALI	72	514	914	1500
NON-NEPALI	59	664	777	1500
TOTAL	131	1178	1691	3000

Chi-square value =31.5,df=2,p=<0.001

Highly significant at even at 0.1% level

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dermatoglyphics of a high altitude Peruvian population and inter population comparisons has been done by Baca O.R (2001 spring). Plantar and digital dermatoglyphics in Malawi has been done by Igibigi P.S (1999). Their studies showing that finger prints indicate population differences. According to that this research has been followed.

Nobody has been done in this work comparing Nepali and Non-Nepali fingerprints. Bilateral variation in finger print pattern amongst Nepali Females & Males are not significantly different (except small significant different in the pattern amongst males, perhaps this may be due to small sample size). Similarly bilateral variations amongst Non-Nepali are also significant. But when the variations for the Nepali & Non-Nepali are considered, there are found to be quite significant.

There is no significant different in Bilateral variation of finger print pattern in Nepali Females (Table No –2), however the bilateral variation Nepali males is significant at 5% level (Table No –3).

Bilateral variation in finger print pattern of Nepali (Both sexes considered together) are also not significant (Table No –4). There is no significant different in types of finger print pattern amongst Non-Nepali Females (Table No –5) and Males (Table No –6). Similarly there is no significant different in bilateral variation of finger print pattern amongst Non-Nepali (Both sex considered together) Table No –7). There are significant group variations in finger print pattern (RT. Hand) between Nepali & Non-Nepali the different is slightly significant. Group variations for left hand prints between Nepali & Non-Nepali are also highly significant. Group variations for both hands between Nepali & Non-Nepali are also highly significant.

CONCLUSION

From this study, it needs to be concluded/inferred that finger print pattern between RT-Hand & LT-Hand of Nepali (or) of Non-Nepali are not significant. There are significant differences in group variation when finger print pattern of both Nepali & Non-Nepali are considered together. This difference is likely to be due to difference in Nationality. The Nepali may have distinct racial trait compared to the Non-Nepali who are mostly of Indian. This study is also only exploratory larger study may be more conclusive.

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